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CLEWS-based Energy Planning Scenarios for Cost Optimization and Climate Change in Thailand

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Executive Summary

This study employs a CLEWs based OSeMOSYS modelling framework to investigate Thailand's energy transition pathways under scenarios of cost optimization and climate change impacts. With electricity demand projected to increase by 81% between 2023 and 2055, the baseline scenario demonstrates that cost optimization favors a gradual phase-out of natural gas in favor of renewable energy technologies—biomass, solar, wind, and hydropower. This transition reduces dependence on imported fuels, lowers long-term system costs, and supports Thailand's decarbonization commitments.

The results highlight important cross-sectoral trade-offs. Renewable expansion, particularly biomass, creates competition for land and may accelerate deforestation while shifting agricultural land use from irrigated to rainfed systems. Water allocation also emerges as a critical constraint, with increased demand for agriculture and cooling water in the energy sector. Under the IPCC A2 climate change scenario, reduced precipitation and lower crop productivity intensify pressures on both food security and water resources, requiring additional investments in irrigation.

These findings underscore the necessity of adopting integrated resource planning approaches that incorporate energy–land–water interlinkages and climate risks. While the model provides insights into optimal energy pathways, further research should address data limitations and explore alternative scenarios, including nuclear development, to inform robust long-term policy decisions.

1. Introduction

Thailand is the ninth largest economy in Asia¹, with the major sector include industrial sector, tourism and financial services are the major sector. The electricity demand for Thailand is projected to increase up to 81% in 2055 due to its forecasted industrial development and GDP growth (baseline 1.9% GDP growth in 2023 according to World Bank Data²). However, the energy sector is responsible for greater than 70% of greenhouse gas emission in Thailand. In response Thailand has issued an 'Alternative Energy Development Plan' in its national leading policy publication 'Power Development Plan (2024)'. Thailand made commitments in its nationally determined contribution (NDC) of COP25 to reduce the carbon emission up to 30-40% in 2030, achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 and meet its net zero target in 2065³.

Another key economic sector of Thailand is agriculture which contribute to 10 percent of GDP and employ 33 percent of labour force; cultivating rice, rubber, fruit, palm oils as its core crops alongside a combination of other crops for domestic consumption and export. Thailand is also vulnerable to climate change impacts (climate vulnerability index 62 out of 181 according to World Bank data⁴) including severe floods, drought and rising temperature⁵ which largely affect agricultural production. Agricultural sector contributes only 8 % of GDP⁶ (ACIAR, 2022), yet it is significant for the food supply and employment in Thailand (33% of labor force). The agricultural sector and energy sector often interlink in various ways. The issues of land use competition between agriculture crops and biofuel crops have been recognized in its energy policy planning.⁷ It is crucial for Thailand to promote its agricultural sector for food supply and export earnings while it encounters increasing energy consumption for its industrial, transportation and residential use.

This study approaches the energy planning of Thailand from the nexus lens of climate land energy and water interlinkages. The major focus of the study is to find out the cost optimization pathway to plan future energy development in Thailand by considering its energy policy goals to address energy security and decarbonization. With a cost optimization results of technology use (land use categories, powerplants, water resources) acting as a baseline business as usual scenario, the study explores the implications of energy planning for land use changes, water supply and food security.

The study outlined here compares the baseline scenario with climate change impacts scenario that follows the A2 formulated emission scenarios developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) as part of their Special Report on Emissions Scenarios (SRES), published in 2000. With this scenario, the study highlights

¹ <https://www.apec2022.go.th/about-thailand/>

² <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?locations=TH>

³ (PDP 2024 draft unofficial translation)

⁴ https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/2021-08/15853-WB_Thailand%20Country%20Profile-WEB_0.pdf

⁵ <https://www.undp.org/stories/climate-impact-thailand>

⁶ <https://www.aciar.gov.au/publication/aop2020/thailand>

⁷ PDP 2024 draft, unofficial translation

the climate change impacts (changes in precipitation and less productivity of land) on energy, land use and food production.

2. Methodology

This study uses CLEW model with OseMOSYS, to analyse the interlinkage between energy, land and water in Thailand using different scenarios. OSeMOSYS is the demand led and bottom up model based on optimizing technology choices. The CLEW framework enables the simultaneous consideration of issue relevant to land, energy and water sectors and their impact on, and vulnerability to, climate change. (IAEA, 2024⁸) The data sources that were used in the CLEW model are secondary data from FAOSTAT, some publicly available data from Thailand's official website and World Bank. The model horizon is 2020-2055 with 2020-2023 calibrated to historical data and 2024-2055 the model optimization years.

The inputs considered in the model are land and water resources, and primary energy sources (fossil fuel and renewable sources). Land and water resources inputs are calculated for different needs (energy, agriculture and public supply). Thus, the model integrated the options for imported natural gas and imported crops to obtain a financial consideration of comparison of domestic and imported gas and crops. In energy, the technology (powerplants) choices available include both fossil fuel- - oil and gas power plant, coal power plant - and renewable power plants- solar, wind, hydropower and biomass plants. The different land uses technologies include agriculture, forest land, built-up land, water bodies and other land uses.

As the baseline scenario, the cost optimization among various technologies across the energy, land and water sectors is calculated to meet the increasing electricity demand and crop production in 2055.

⁸ INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, The Climate, Land, Energy and Water Framework, IAEA-TECDOC-2065, IAEA, Vienna (2024), <https://doi.org/10.61092/iaea.uuu5-lz0i>

Reference Energy System of Thailand

Figure 1: Reference Energy System of Thailand based on CLEWS model

Another scenario is developed to understand climate change impacts across different sectors (power generation and agricultural crop production). This scenario considered the expected changes in precipitation from the year 2035 up to 2055 with less crop productivity from land. It aims to further explore how climate change affects the long-term power sector development and food security in Thailand.

Using the CLEWS-OSeMOSYS Linear Programming Energy System Model the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Baseline Scenario (BAU)	Cost optimization for power generation to meet increasing projected electricity demand in 2055	What is the cost optimization pathway for Thailand to generate the electricity needed for projected GDP growth in 2055? Does cost optimization reflect the decarbonization goals in national climate and energy policy of Thailand?
Climate Change Scenario	The A2 climate scenario is one of the emission scenarios developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) as part of their Special Report on Emissions Scenarios (SRES), published in 2000).	What are the projected impacts of the IPCC's A2 climate change scenarios on land use, crop patterns and water usage for Thailand?

3. Results

Figure 2(a): Electricity Demand of Thailand by 2055
 Figure 2(b): Total Power Production by 2055 (Baseline scenario)

Electricity demand of Thailand is projected to grow up to 81 percent from 741 PJ in 2023 to 1349 PJ in 2055. This projection is based on the GDP growth of 1.9% in historical year (2020-2023).

The baseline scenario suggests a cost optimization pathway for Thailand by gradually phasing out expensive gas fired power plants by expanding renewable particularly biomass, solar power plants, wind and hydropower plants. This implies that renewable energy generation such as solar, biomass and wind power plant in the long term can offer least cost for electricity generation in Thailand. In the context of energy security, this is an important consideration as Thailand is currently reliant on importing extensive amounts of natural gas at high cost (Thailand imported 21,767.000 Cub meter mn of natural gas in Dec 2023⁹ at the total value of 8,396,171.04 thousand USD¹⁰).

The least cost scenario not only achieves the cost optimization for Thailand in making financial investment in power production but also promote the decarbonization goals by significantly reducing emission from fossil fuel-based power plant. (Figure 3) The cost optimization pathway will also be the ultimate solution for the existing energy policy problem of Thailand (mainly dependence on natural gas). It suggests that Thailand can achieve energy transition while also addressing energy security in the long run within cost optimization pathway. In other words, there is no long-term economic argument to use fossil fuels in Thailand’s future energy profile.

⁹ <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/indicator/thailand/natural-gas-imports>

¹⁰ <https://wits.worldbank.org/trade/comtrade/en/country/THA/year/2023/tradeflow/Imports/partner/ALL/product/271111>

Figure 3: Total Emission under Baseline Scenario (M Ton)

The baseline scenario which prioritize the cost optimization by phasing out fossil fuel, however, has significant implications for land use changes, agricultural crop production, water resources management.

Figure 4: Land Use under BAU and Climate Change Scenario

One of the consequences of investing in renewable energy (particularly biomass power plant) is land use competition. In the baseline, it is evident that Thailand will encounter deforestation by clearing some forest land areas to expand crop production (including palm oil production as a fuel crop for biomass and other major crops; rice, rubber and other crops). A slight increase in urban areas is also expected. As a result, the irrigated crop areas will decline, and rainfed crop production will become the primary method for major crops. This could be because the irrigation costs significantly higher than rainfed plantation although it can boost the crop productivity.

Figure 5: Comparison of Water Demand between Baseline and Climate Change Scenario

In the baseline scenario, the water resources required for agriculture and cooling water for thermal power plants while the water saved can be allocated more for public water use (mainly with increasing availability of surface water).

However, the increasing threat of climate change (less water availability and less crop productivity) will put significant pressure on public water supply and crop production. The decline in water availability will drive the need for irrigation in turn in the long run, and will create a significant financial burden for Thailand.

As a result, all renewable energy generation (mainly biomass and solar power plant) accounts for the majority of the total annual investment costs whereas the investment for public water supply and agricultural water supply also became a significant cost. Climate change impacts (less water availability and drought) will drive the investment cost up ~6% from 234,450 USD to 248,982 USD.

4. Discussion

The Cost optimization scenario (baseline) promote energy transition for Thailand in 2055. It also reflects decarbonization goals in national energy and climate mitigation policies. It addresses major policy question of how Thailand can tackle energy security in the future by decreasing its dependence on natural gas, and lower the financial investment in natural gas. However, climate change is a significant threat across different sectors (energy, agriculture, public water needs and natural resource constraints). Power generation will compete resources (mainly water and land) with agricultural crop production, food and water supply in the future.

Potential policy and action to take for Thailand is to lay out strategies and policies for resource allocation in the admist of climate change. Inclusion of various crosssectorial multistakeholder groups (industrial business, agricultural producers, energy consumers, forest user groups, etc.) to find out optimal resource allocation options.

The study has certain limitations in terms of data and its assumptions. The secondary data that was used in the model were from different sources such as FAO, World Bank, IAEA and some official and unofficial publicly available data. Some energy statistics may have certain variation from official statistics in Thailand.

The study suggests future work for different climate change scenarios (the impacts of temperature rises and natural disaster such as floods and storm on crop production and energy generation. In addition, Thailand proposed action for energy planning in the future (based on Power Development Plan 2024) favours promotion of small modular nuclear power plants in its power generation. It will be crucial to further explore the investment options for including nuclear by considering the cooling water needs, land areas for construction of power plant and land areas required for nuclear waste treatments, and further costs.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that Thailand's future energy transition can be achieved through a cost-optimized pathway emphasizing renewable energy, which simultaneously enhances energy security and supports decarbonization goals. However, the analysis also reveals cross-sectoral challenges, including land use competition, water constraints, and heightened vulnerabilities under climate change scenarios. Addressing these interlinkages requires integrated planning that balances energy, agriculture, and water needs. The climate change will cost Thailand 6 % more annual investment cost than baseline scenario over the model period. Future research should refine data inputs, test additional climate scenarios, and evaluate alternative technologies such as nuclear energy to provide a more comprehensive basis for sustainable and resilient policy-making.

References

ACIAR (2022) Thailand retrieved from
<https://www.aciar.gov.au/publication/aop2020/thailand>

INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, The Climate, Land, Energy and Water Framework, IAEA-TECDOC-2065, IAEA, Vienna (2024),
<https://doi.org/10.61092/iaea.uiu5-lz0j>

Power Development Plan (2024) Unofficial translation

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